

THE USING OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES ON IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF THE GRAPE HARVEST AND THEIR EFFECTIVENESS

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Abstract. The article provides information about the importance of thinning grape clusters, berries and bagging of grape clusters in increasing the quality of the grape harvest, and the effect on the quality and quantity of the harvest. Also, changes in the composition of the grape berries and the color of the skin are given when used the above activities are carried out to vine. There are flower thinning, cluster thinning and berry thinning types. Among the bags, the paper bag was the most effective.

Key words: Grape, quality, flower thinning, cluster thinning, berry thinning, cluster bagging, paper bag, chemical composition, pigmentation.

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ ПО ПОВЫШЕНИЮ КАЧЕСТВА СБОРА ВИНОГРАДА И ИХ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ

Аннотация. В статье представлена информация о значении прореживания гроздей винограда, ягод и пакетирования гроздей винограда в повышении качества урожая винограда, а также о влиянии на качество и количество урожая. Также даны изменения в составе ягод винограда и цвете кожицы при применении вышеперечисленных мероприятий, проводимых на лозе. Различают прореживание цветков, прореживание гроздей и прореживание ягод. Среди мешков бумажный пакет оказался самым эффективным.

Ключевые слова: Виноград, качество, прореживание цветков, прореживание гроздей, прореживание ягод, расфасовка гроздей, бумажный пакет, химический состав, пигментация.

Introductions

In recent years, extensive activities have been carried out in the Republic of Uzbekistan to create new varieties and hybrids of grapes with high yield, resistant to widespread dangerous diseases and pests, and to develop optimal agro technologies of cultivation. Nevertheless, there is a need to carry out additional work on improving the quality of the grape harvest, which plays an important role in increasing the export potential of the grape harvest. Grape cluster, berry thinning and putting bags on grape clusters are also important in improving the quality of grape harvest.

Hugo Oliveira de Silva (2008), Virginia Beasley (2020), San Luis Obispo (2011), A.K.Parker (2012), S.F.Wheeler (2006) and others have conducted scientific research on improving the quality of table varieties of winegrape in Italy, Spain and France, South America, Argentina, Chile, Peru, as well as Japan and other countries.

Methods

Thinning is the practice of adjusting crop level during the growing season. It is achieved in two fundamental ways: altering the number of clusters per vine and altering the size of clusters.

How many clusters lefting on a vine depends on the variety being grown, the size of the vine, the use of cultural practices that alter the size of clusters, the desired crop level and year-to-year variations in vine fruitfulness.

Fruiting is an exhaustive process to the tree especially if the crop is heavy.

The other objectives of fruit thinning are the following:

1. To increase the annual yield of marketable fruit;
2. To improve the fruit size;
3. To improve the color of the fruit;
4. To improve the quality of fruit;
5. It reduces the limb breakage;
6. It promotes tree vigor and ensures more regular cropping;
7. It permits more thorough spraying and dusting of fruits during the late season application;
8. It ensures uniform ripening.

Time of thinning at blossom timing, thinning is done at marble stage. Soon after the natural fruit drop of young fruits has started.

Methods of thinning:

1. Hand thinning;
2. Chemical thinning.

Results

When a grower is unable or unwilling to locate more accurate information for crop adjustment of temperate-climate table grapes, it will be useful to know that vines with typical vine spacings and medium-sized clusters will produce a moderate yield of 4 tons per acre with 24 clusters/vine. Therefore, begin in the first year of production by thinning to 24 clusters per vine. Then, after the first harvest, decide if that number needs to be increased or decreased in subsequent years.

Cluster thinning. Many table grape varieties have naturally compact clusters susceptible to berry cracking and fruit rot. In such situations, flower cluster thinning is hazardous. It is best to adjust crop size by thinning clusters after fruit set (Fig. 1). As a generalization, the greater the number of clusters on a vine during bloom, the fewer berries that will set on each cluster. Such reduced fruit set may help to reduce cluster compactness and fruit rot. It may also allow the berries on the clusters room to enlarge without creating excessively compact clusters. Therefore, whenever cluster compactness is a concern, use cluster thinning rather than flower cluster thinning to adjust crop level, even though it is more difficult and more costly.

Figure 1.

After fruit set, when all berry shatter has occurred, all clusters in this temporary fruiting zone are removed along with any additional clusters that need to be removed from the primary fruiting zone.

Berry thinning. Berry thinning is very useful to modify cluster shape when a variety has elongated, straggly clusters. Flower cluster thinning may increase the cluster compactness of long, straggly clusters to produce large, showy clusters.

Berry thinning produces smaller, globular, more manageable clusters than flower cluster thinning by pinching off the lower portion of the cluster immediately after fruit set. This increases both cluster compactness and berry size on the remaining portion of the cluster. Because berry thinning creates smaller, lighter clusters than either flower cluster thinning or cluster thinning, more clusters can be retained on the vine to produce the same size crop. This practice should be used only on varieties with loose clusters. Flower cluster thinning and berry thinning are good strategies for increasing cluster compactness.

It's best to limit young vines to one cluster per shoot. This is called fruit thinning. Thin fruit right before bloom to improve fruit set on the remaining clusters. Fruit thinning can also be done later in the season, if you feel you haven't pruned the vine severely enough and there's too much fruit for the crop to ripen well. If removed fruit clusters before veraison, berry size increases, yield is less affected, and the grape clusters ripen sooner. If you thin fruit soon after veraison, there is little effect on berry size, but yield is reduced, and the remaining fruit ripens sooner. In general, shoots need to be at least 3 feet long to support a fruit crop. Remove clusters from shorter shoots.

Fruit bagging is an agricultural practice (or a physical protection technique) that helps to produce high quality fruit and is common in many countries such as Japan, China, and Spain. This practice is commonly applied to several species, and the resulting products have higher visual quality through the promotion of peel coloration and reduction of fruit cracking and russeting. The bagging technique can modify the microenvironment to improve fruit development, which may result in several changes in internal fruit quality, as is the case for grapes produced under plastic coverings. Bagging has been used extensively in several fruit crops with different aims, such as improvement of skin color or reduction of incidence of diseases, insect pests, mechanical damage, skin sunburn, agrochemical residues, and bird damage. In table grapes, bagging leads to bunches more uniform in berry skin coloration, although several studies indicated that pre-harvest fruit bagging can both promote and inhibit fruit color development.

The bagging technique, which was first utilized in Japan in the 20th century for pears and grapes, is now widely applied in Asian countries (Japan, China, Korea), Australia and the USA, protecting fruits from the surrounding environment (mainly from light and pathogens, then stresses related to temperature, water/humidity, and air movement) with a sort of shield—a physical barrier around the fruit.

Conclusion

Thinning is the practice of adjusting crop level during the growing season. By the thinning we can increase size, quality (sugar and pigment amount) of berries and we can change amount of harvest of grapewine.

Effects of bagging on the quality of the fruit, particularly on the effects on the external color, which is one of the main quality attributes of the fruit, taking for granted the protection

provided by the bag against pathogens, pests or mechanical damages. Bagging technique is used specifically to enhance fruit appearance and quality, especially in Asia.

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